

The Differences Between Machine Translation and Human Translation from The Perspective of Literary Texts*

Dai Jia-ni¹, Shen Hui-jia², Zhuo Jing³, Pan Xiang-yin⁴, Yuan Zi Yan⁵

^{1,2,3,4,5}Zhejiang University of Finance & Economics Dongfang College

Abstract: *The translation industry has developed rapidly and has been got more and more attention. This research studies the differences between machine translation and human translation from the perspective of literary texts, and provides an in-depth understanding of the advantages and disadvantages of machine translation and human translation. Through literature method, induction method and empirical method, it is found that human translation is more flexible and dynamic, while machine translation is less capable of identifying grammatical and logical errors, etc., and is more programmed compared to human translation. In view of this, we acknowledge that machine translation will take up more translation tasks, but it will not completely replace human translation.*

Key Words : *literary text; Machine translation; Human translation; Pros and cons*

I. Introduction

At present, China's language service industry still has a long way to go, and there will be many hardships and dangers waiting to be overcome on the way. Artificial intelligence is developing rapidly, and the accuracy of translation has been improved much more than before. Although machine translation can facilitate people's access to foreign information as well as improve the work efficiency of professional translators, it is necessary to rely on human translators for an in-depth exchange of ideas, and the position of human translation is irreplaceable. Therefore, through this survey and research, we conduct a study to compare the gap between machine translation and human translation by reading a review of the current status of domestic and foreign research.

* Fund Project : "On C-E Translation of TCM Terminology From the Perspective of Chinese Culture Going-out Policy" of Scientific Research Training Program of Zhejiang University of Finance & Economics Dongfang College in 2021(Project No.2021dfx080)

II. The Research Significance of the Difference Between Machine Translation and Human Translation

2.1 Theoretical significance

With the continuous development of translation, people pursue the improvement of translation quality, and the quality of translation of literary texts is particularly strict. The study of the respective superiority and limitation of both helps to seek the future optimized development direction of machine translation and human translation, and provide better services to translators and readers. It helps people from different countries to communicate more accurately. [4]

2.2 Practical significance

It is beneficial to better understand the differences between machine translation and human translation when translating literary texts, so that constructive suggestions can be provided on the future development direction of machine translation and human translation for optimizing the translation of literary texts; it is beneficial to the internationalization of machine translation and human translation of literary texts. [6]By comparing human translation and machine translation in terms of accuracy, fluency and limitations, our group finds that human translation is clearly superior in both complex sentences and noun phrases. The existence of a large number of polysemous words in English, even if machine translation is supported by the powerful Internet and electronic dictionaries, it will lead to the inability of machine translation with technical limitations to select the correct word meaning, which greatly hinders the improvement of machine translation. [7]

III. Investigation of the Use of Human or Machine Translation

3.1 Preparation for investigation

First of all, after the group discussion and agreement, we will have a deeper understanding of this topic by reviewing relevant information, then carry out research activities in the form of online questionnaires and interview, and analyze and propose solutions according to the investigation situation.

Finally, according to this core research direction, the steps and time plan for conducting were prepared, and the original plan was specifically as follows:

Phase 1: April-August 2021

(1) Collect and review relevant literature, analyze the current situation of domestic and foreign research and review the current situation.

Through the search on Internet, it can be seen that domestic scholars' research on machine translation and human translation mainly focuses on the relationship and comparison between the two and their future development under different backgrounds, and few scholars have studied the gap between them. In the past 19 years (2003-2021), there are about 15 journal articles on machine translation and human translation, which core

journals are not included.

At present, there are still many technical difficulties to be overcome in machine translation, such as disordered word order, inaccurate word meaning and isolated syntactic analysis.

For these reasons, we will investigate the differences between machine translation and human translation. We will understand the shortcomings of machine translation and human translation in various aspects and why it is impossible for machine translation to replace human translation in the current situation.

(2) According to the expected value and results, the research situation, research angle and research method of the subject have been adjusted.

(3) Analyze the problems and design the questionnaire

① The preliminary conclusion obtained by synthesis

② Enter the design stage of the questionnaire

Based on the proposed arguments and questions, we started to design the initial questionnaire framework and content, and determined the total input of questionnaire and population.

Phase 2: September to December 2021

Continue to complete the data collection and collation, and we finish the unfinished work in the early stage; at the same time, based on the initial work, further understand the differences between human translation and machine translation. Improve the questionnaire survey designed in the early stage and put it on the crowds, collect the questionnaires, organize the data and conduct preliminary analysis.

(1) Electronic questionnaire

① In the in-depth analysis, Digging *The Differences between Machine Translation and Human Translation from the Perspective of Literary Texts*, *The Differences between Machine Translation and Human Translation, A comparative study of machine translation for multilingual sentence-level sentiment analysis* and *The Gap Between Machine Translation and Human Translation from the Perspective of Literary Texts*, we further improved the questionnaire and formed the final draft.

② After the questionnaire was put out, students were actively called on to fill it out, and a total of 80 questionnaires were collected. After sorting and summarizing the collected questionnaires, accurate and effective data are obtained.

Based on the data and results of the questionnaire survey, the advantages and disadvantages of machine translation and human translation are highlighted, and the differences between machine translation and human translation are more obvious.

Phase 3: January-March 2022

(1) Complete the interview with classmates

(2) Start to analyze the data and materials that have been sorted out (mainly the data of the questionnaire and the analysis of the questionnaire responses) and prepare the concluding materials.

3.2 Implementation and Adjustment of Investigation Plan

3.2.1 Plan implementation

According to the plan, the first stage of the team is mainly to consult relevant literature, collect relevant information ; the second stage around the design of questionnaire, collect relevant data ; the third stage will compare the results of the analysis, according to the relevant literature and the obtained survey data integration and depth analysis, so as to draw a preliminary conclusion.

3.2.2 Plan adjustment

The first stage is mainly to collect information, the workload is relatively large and requires a lot of time. Therefore, our team members in the summer vacation assigned their needs to consult the information, launched the work of information collection. The second stage is mainly from November to December. Our team designed a series of questions with the theme of 'the difference between machine translation and manual translation' to conduct a questionnaire survey on students around us. The third phase is mainly carried out after school return, that is, from February to March. With the active cooperation of students, we quickly got a series of initial data. On this basis, we analyzed these data. By integrating the relevant literature and combining the literature and data together, we makes a horizontal comparative analysis, and draws a series of conclusions on the differences between machine translation and manual translation in literary texts.

3.3 questionnaire survey

The electronic questionnaire was distributed through wechat Moments, QQ Zone and other network social media platforms. The respondents were mainly college students in Oriental College of Zhejiang University of Finance and Economics. The questionnaire content mainly focused on the frequency of using machine translation, the problems and advantages of machine translation and human translation.

3.3.1 The questionnaire is generated

Questionnaire through the questionnaire star small program production generation. In order to formulate the questions more suitable for college students, our team members through introspection, but also through the interview of classmates.

After modification and discussion, the final version of the questionnaire issued to the public was generated. The following figure is the two-dimensional code of the final board questionnaire. The specific contents of the questionnaire will be attached to the end of the report (see the final attachment of the report for details) :

3.3.2 Questionnaire survey results

This questionnaire survey is mainly aimed at college students, and the majority of post-00s. And the questionnaire results are basically in line with our assumptions. The electronic time is 9 March 2022 questionnaire distributed solstice on March 16, 80 questionnaire distributed, grade layer covers the freshman to senior, among them, fill in the questionnaire, is engaged in the translation of professional and has nothing to do professional proportion were 37.04% and 62.96% respectively, the number of overall coverage is scattered, not limited foreign languages institute, It has certain reference value.

3.3.3 Analysis of questionnaire results

A total of 80 valid questionnaires were collected in this survey, and the following is an analysis of the questionnaire data.

(1) Crowd Selection

figure1: Crowd Selection 1

As seen in Figure 1, the people who participated in our electronic questionnaire are currently enrolled in college and have many advantages. For example, they have a strong sense of responsibility, professionalism, good social etiquette and interpersonal communication skills. First of all, the college students can understand the original design of our electronic questionnaire, and can listen patiently to our explanation of the reasons for participating in the survey, and secondly, we can stimulate the enthusiasm of the respondents to participate in the survey.

(2) Age Stage

figure2:Age Stage

As shown in Figure 2, 88.9% of the college students who participated in our electronic questionnaire are mostly post-00s, while only 11.1% are post-90s. Compared with the post-90s, the "post-00s" refers to the young generation born between 2000 and 2009, who were born in the third decade after the reform and opening up, coinciding with the golden decade of China's rapid economic growth, enjoying the great achievements of reform and opening up at birth, growing up together with the Internet. They have more open eyes, broader interests and more diversified and compatible ideas, which injects more fresh blood into our electronic questionnaire. The content of this questionnaire mainly focuses on the frequency of machine translation, what are the problems and advantages of machine translation and human translation.

(3) Is the profession related to translation

figure3:Is the profession related to translation

37.04% of the college students in our electronic questionnaire were engaged in or had careers related to translation, 62.96% were not related to translation. Some were majoring in social work. Some were majoring in auditing, and some of us were majoring in English. All of our majors were different, but none of them affected a specific knowledge and love of translation. It is possible that students in this major have better listening and speaking skills who translate more grammatically and linguistically, but that doesn't stop you from translating English works through constant practice after class. Language is a skill that needs to be built up over time and requires a lot of energy and resources. Non-majors can also deal with native English speakers. In fact, it is easier to

approach each other by taking the initiative to communicate with them, from small voice, intonation, to large cultural information. If your boss or client is British or American, he or she will trust you more because of your language and cultural affinity.

(4) Frequency of using translation software

figure4:Frequency of using translation software

The graph shows that 59.26% of the students often use translation software, 33.3% use it occasionally, and 7.41% rarely use it. Most of the translation software has a simple and fast process, and the translation time control can be accurately estimated. The essence of translation software is machine translation. In the context of the Internet, translation software, as a kind of machine translation, is quietly changing people's learning methods and behavioral habits with the power of information technology. Therefore, this questionnaire is of great theoretical and practical significance in analyzing the frequency of using translation software by college students.

(5) The relationship between machine translation and human translation

figure5: The relationship between machine translation and human translation

62.96% of university students think that machine translation and human translation will be a mutual help relationship, 3.7% think it will be a competitive relationship, and 33.3% think it will be a symbiotic relationship. In fact, what everyone said is very reasonable. With the development of technology, the quality of machine translation has been greatly improved. And the advantage of machine translation in terms of cost and speed has caused some influence on human translation, but machines have their inherent weaknesses and flaws. Translation

needs to be based on a precise understanding of the original text, even to avoid or recreate the flaws of the original text. Many experts believe that the development of machine translation will definitely eliminate low-end translators, but it is almost impossible to completely replace human translators. A few days ago, Google warned users not to replace human translators with machine translators. Therefore, what students need to do is to strengthen their own learning and improve their translation skills. Human translation will not only not die out, but also be favored. Secondly, the relationship between the two should be symbiotic, machine translation appears only after the pavement of human translation, and the two themselves are a symbiotic relationship. Human translation can correct the wrong expressions of some machine translation, increase the accuracy, and be rich in the real emotion of human translation. And machine translation can improve the speed and efficiency of human translation, and the two complement each other.

(6) Translations that are mainly relied on in daily life

figure6: Translations that are mainly relied on in daily life

The graph shows that 55.56% of college students rely on machine translation, while 44.4% of students rely on human translation. Relatively speaking, the number of machine translation is a bit more, and machine translation is relatively more convenient and faster, saving time. The proportion of human translation is also very high. For college students, in fact, human translation can bring us a lot of benefits, for example, it can improve our translation ability and we can learn more English words and grammar .

(7) Translations that are mainly relied on in formal communication

figure7: Translations that are mainly relied on in formal communication

As seen from the graph, 85.19% of people rely on human translation in communication, and the rest rely on machine translation. The side reflects the importance and irreplaceability of human translation, which always comes first in real communication. Human translation can be more recognized in foreign affairs communication, can better express the emotions of both sides, can make them better express each other's meaning in communication, make the communication more affinity and reduce the inconvenience caused by most cultural differences.

(8) Which translation software is currently in use

figure8: Which translation software is currently in use

62.96% of college students use Youdao translation, 48.15% of them use Baidu translation, 18.52% of them like to use Google translation, and 44.44% of them use other software. In fact, including myself, the proportion of using Youdao translation is larger, relatively speaking, Youdao translation and Baidu translation will become the first choice, and the probability of using Baidu is also great, and I believe that the first time we encounter problems is to open Baidu. Google Translate is relatively less used, and the value is relatively low. The use of other software also accounted for 44.4%.

(9) Problems with translation software

figure9: Problems with translation software

96.3% of college students think that the quality (accuracy) of translation needs to be improved because most translation software sometimes does not make sense and sometimes translates a sentence to mean something else, for example, hole take a rain check may mean next appointment on a rainy day, but what it actually means is another day, not a specific appointment on a rainy day. 37.4% of college students think that some translation software charges too much. 37.4% of them think that some translation software charges too much. Some software do require membership to enjoy more benefits, such as Fanbei Word, which allows you to see root words only after you open a membership. 18.52% of college students think that the software design is inconvenient to use. Some software design is too high-end, indeed a little ungrounded.

(10) Advantages of Machine Translation

figure10: Advantages of Machine Translation

88.89% of college students think that machine translation is fast and convenient, and indeed using machine translation saves more time and direct translation is relatively simple. 70.37% of them think that machine translation is highly practical, and the original purpose of machine translation is to facilitate people and solve problems in a more practical way when they encounter translation problems.

(11) Advantages of Human Translation

figure11: Advantages of Human Translation

Most college students agree that human translation has the advantages of dealing with cultural differences effectively, better readability, higher accuracy, fewer errors in syntactic analysis, more rational sentence structure, and higher thoughtfulness.

(12) Problems with human translation

figure12: Problems with human translation

74.07% of college students think that there is the problem of uneven quality of human translation, 51.85% think there is the problem of misunderstanding, 14.81% think there are other problems, 55.56% think that the fees for human translation are relatively high, and the price is really different for different translation quality. Another 37.04% think that manual translation is slow and inefficient.

(13) The impact of translation software on English learning

figure13: The impact of translation software on English learning

55.56% of college students think that translation software can provide ideas for English learning, but do not rely on it too much; 18.52% of them think that translation software can make us rely on it too much, which is not good for English learning; 25.93% of college students think that translation software can save a lot of time and is worth learning; no students think that translation software has misleading errors and should not be trusted completely. This also reflects that the advantages of translation software outweigh the disadvantages, and it is still worthwhile for us to use and learn. However, we should not over-rely on them, for over-reliance will greatly reduce our English learning ability, and moderation is enough.

(14) Accuracy of the machine translation used

figure14: Accuracy of the machine translation used

81.48% of college students think that machine translation is basically accurate, 14.81% think it is accurate, and only 3.7% think it is not accurate. This data reflects that the accuracy of machine translation is high, which can be used and referred to when encountering translation problems, and shows that machine translation has become an indispensable part of our life.

(15) What should be improved in today's machine translation

figure15: What should be improved in today's machine translation

85.19% of college students think that machine translation should greatly improve the accuracy, and 55.56% of them think that machine translation should improve the grammatical problem of discourse order. The graph fully illustrates that the accuracy of machine translation should be greatly improved. Relatively speaking, the human translation is longer but still more accurate in terms of accuracy, and the problem of intonation grammar of machine translation also accounts for 55.56%. The problem of intonation grammar is also a very important issue and worthy of the object of our time and attention.

IV. A Comparative Study of Translation Gap Between Artificial Translation and Machine Translation in Literary Texts

With the development of science and technology, machine translation is more and more widely used in people's daily life, but manual translation is still an indispensable part. In this process, many differences between the two translation methods are gradually exposed.

4.1 A Comparative Study of Artificial Translation and Machine Translation in Literary Texts

4.1.1 For the overall framework, sentence structure and vocabulary selection of literary texts

In terms of the overall framework of literary texts, machine translation can be basically accurate and complete, so that the basic structure and framework of texts are relatively complete. On the other hand, artificial translation can accurately grasp the overall framework of the text and clearly distinguish the differences between various literary texts, such as poetry, prose, drama and other types of literary texts in the overall framework structure.

In the sentence structure of literary texts, machine translation is slightly inferior. Machine translation often adopts "literal translation", that is to say, according to the words in the original text, they are translated into corresponding Chinese one by one, [2] can not correctly analyze some grammatical rules existing in sentences, so it often produces some obvious grammatical errors, resulting in unsmooth sentence meaning, which affects readers'

grasp of the overall content of the material; On the contrary, manual translation can make up for the shortcomings of machine translation. Manual translation can give full play to the subjective initiative, better convert the original text to Chinese, select the sentence pattern that can best convey the meaning of the original text, and accurately express the meaning of the sentence, so that readers can understand the original text more easily.^[10]

In terms of vocabulary selection of literary texts, machine translation often makes mistakes. Due to the rapid development of science and technology, machine translation is very fast in the speed of information retrieval due to the support of the Internet, which is one of the advantages of machine translation. However, it is also because of a large amount of data, machine translation often chooses the most commonly used meaning in vocabulary selection, which will lead to ambiguity of some words. Manual translation is more flexible. The translator will choose the lexical meaning according to the theme and connotation conveyed by the whole text, so as to select the optimal vocabulary and convey the meaning of the article more accurately. Thus, for the flexible processing of vocabulary, manual translation is better than machine translation^[4].

4.1.2 The overall language style of literary texts

In terms of the overall language style of literary texts, machine translation is usually "rigid". For example, for the translation of poetry, machine translation can only complete the basic content of poetry, and the language style is only plain and straightforward, which cannot convey the beauty of ancient Chinese traditional culture. However, artificial translators often choose various ways to carve the language repeatedly, such as using antithesis, parallelism and other figure of speech to make the language richer, make the language style more flexible, and can better convey the beauty of ancient poetry and Chinese language.

4.1.3 The characterization of literary texts

For literary texts such as novels, the shaping of characters is particularly critical. Machine translation is often unable to correctly understand the meaning of the sentence, only a rigid translation according to the original text word by word. For example, for the portrait description of characters, 'He was big and shaggy and not a little gruff. He had tawny, heavy-lidded eyes.' Machine translation will translate into 'He was big and strong, not rough at all. His eyes are brown and heavy.' Although such translation is easy to understand in meaning, it lacks certain artistry. Manual translation will translate like this, 'he is tall, his hair is fluffy, and his temper is irritable. A pair of yellow - brown eyes, lashes thick.' It can be seen that manual translation makes full use of the feature that Chinese often uses four-character words in the description of portraits, so that the translation is more accurate and authentic, catchy and vivid at the same time.^[5]

4.1.4 The emotional expression of literary texts

In the aspect of emotional expression of literary texts, machine translation is very deficient in terms of emotional expression due to the lack of various emotions contained in human beings. Machines are subjects without life and thought, and only human beings can fully understand and feel the expression of different emotions,

so machine translation cannot accurately convey the emotional colors contained in the translation. Machine translation often just copy the surface meaning of the original text, which may be able to express the emotion of the translation superficially, but it can not accurately convey the 'hidden meaning' of the translation to the reader, which will greatly reduce the effect of understanding. Artificial translation can 'free translation' on the basis of understanding the translation of the original text, and later processing it, so as to convey the true feelings of the author in the translation, make the reader resonate with it, better understand the translation and arise deep thoughts.

4.1.5 For the cultural connotation of literary texts

There are great differences between the two translation methods in the cultural connotation of literary texts. Language is not only the surface text, but also has the accompanying cultural color. In manual translation, translators can flexibly adopt various ways to supplement and explain the missing cultural information, such as annotation and explanation. However, machine translation has not yet reached this level, so the translated version often has the phenomenon of disconnection and logical confusion, which makes the readers read a little harder and unable to better understand the original text. At the same time, it also ignores the cultural connotation contained in it, and makes the translation lose its cultural value.

4.2 Compare the Views of Different Scholars on the Two Translation Methods

4.2.1 Domestic scholars

Most scholars believe that there are still many differences between machine translation and manual translation from the perspective of literary texts. For highly specialized texts such as law, science and technology, people can combine machine translation and manual translation for research. In information retrieval, even machine translation is better. In the translation of literary texts, machine translation is still slightly inadequate. In the translation of literary texts, artificial translation has more flexibility, randomness, initiative and continuous optimization. The translation of literary texts pays more attention to artistry, which requires continuous thinking, processing and optimization of human translators in the later stage, and thus obtains more artistically valuable translation texts. Machine translation tends to be more biased towards some academic texts and more practical. Therefore, in the translation of literary texts, the emotional color, cultural connotation and even deeper thematic communication are often ignored.

The ultimate goal of artificial translation in literary translation is 'faithfulness, expressiveness and elegance', while machine translation can only achieve 'faithfulness', 'expressiveness' and 'elegance' sometimes cannot be achieved. Therefore, in the translation of literary texts, most scholars prefer manual translation rather than machine translation.

4.2.2 Foreign scholars

Foreign scholars have little research on the gap between machine translation and manual translation in the translation of literary texts, but a few scholars believe that machine translation can convey some human emotions in translation. The research results of foreign scholars show that the machine translation system is mature enough to produce reliable English translation and can be used for sentiment analysis in sentences. Compared with the methods constructed for specific languages, machine translation achieves competitive prediction performance. The results of this study show that machine translation can convey emotions in the translation of certain literary texts.^[1] However, compared with manual translation, machine translation still has shortcomings, which cannot fully and accurately convey the cultural connotation contained in the translation as manual translation does.^[11]

V. Problems and analysis of machine translation and human translation

5.1 Existing problems

5.1.1 Machine translation

Machine translation, also known as automatic translation, is the process of using computers to speak one natural language (source language) into another natural language (target language). As a branch of computational linguistics, it is one of the ultimate goals of artificial intelligence and has important scientific research value.^[3]

As we all know, the difference between English and Chinese is very great, and the difficulty of English-Chinese machine translation will increase accordingly. Although with the progress of The Times and the development of machines, the accuracy rate of machine translation has been improved, the readability and accuracy of the translated articles are still not very high, the results of machine translation are too obvious.

5.1.1.1 Mistakes in word discrimination

Polysemy is a common phenomenon in English. The proper translation of a word needs to be judged by its context, and machine translation cannot rely on context for the time being.

E.g. She is a fox.

To college students, for example, the most commonly used translation software youdao translation translated means "她是一只狐狸", in fact, the translation is correct, but the "fox" in English also has the meaning of "charming fashionable young women", therefore, if you want to have more accurate translation of the sentence, can only rely on artificial to judge the word meaning by the context.^[8]

5.1.1.2 the choice of articles

Chinese has no articles, but English has many demonstrative pronouns equivalent to Chinese "这" and "那". But not all articles need to be translated.

E.g. Turn to the left, and you will find the post office.

We can translate it into “ 向左拐个弯， 你就可以找到邮局”。 Rather than “向这个左侧拐弯， 你就可以找到

这个邮局”。Obviously, if each article is translated like the latter, the sentence will be wordy and verbose.^[9]

5.1.1.3 Translation of proverbs

E.g. 狗嘴里吐不出象牙

Machine translation of Baidu's translation into "No Ivory issues from the mouth of a dog" often fails to consider the special meaning of "dog" in Chinese-English translation. In Chinese, the word "dog" often has a derogatory connotation, while in English-speaking countries, dogs are regarded as the most loyal friends of human beings. Therefore, "dog" often has a positive connotation, such as the most familiar "lucky dog", which means "lucky person". Therefore, this proverb should be translated as "A filthy mouth can't utter decent language" to be more closely related to the Chinese meaning.

5.1.2 Human translation

(1) For human translation, the disadvantage is obvious, that is, low efficiency. A person's energy is often limited, the machine may be a minute to translate the short text, but it will take an hour or even longer time. There is a limit, even to proficiency, to mastery of the language.

(2) The price is high. As we all know, many translation software on the network are free, most of the people who do not have high requirements on the accuracy of translation will choose these free translation software, and the price of human translation is settled by the number of words, so the shortcomings of human translation are exposed.

5.2 The solution

Machine translation can only convey the meaning of the original text to a certain extent, in order to get an accurate translation, or can not do without human translation. In my opinion, the best method is to combine machine translation and human translation by ourselves. In time urgent circumstances, for example, you can use the machine translation is the first draft, and then on the basis of this draft, check with the original, according to the known and error-prone point changes, such as word choice, word meaning discrimination, polysemy, proverb, or proprietary versions are some proper nouns, Some words need to be translated according to the context. Finally, according to the search for information, combined with the context and "faithfulness, expressiveness, elegance" of the three criteria for revision.

This is especially true in the face of translation of different styles, such as expository text, expository text is characterized by the unity of tenses, the general simple present tense, but sometimes in order to express special requirements, some other tenses will be used in individual places, which requires manual translation according to the specific situation of specific analysis. The plain text is the description and introduction of objective things. The translated expression should be as credible and rigorous as possible. Passive voice is preferred in English, which will not be considered in machine translation, so it also needs to be corrected in human translation. Again such as

narrative, a narrative of the statement in many different tone, imperative sentence, exclamatory sentences, and interrogative sentences and so on, if all the machine translation, translation cavity is too heavy, lost narrative to express feelings, at this point, the process of human translation must give these sentences emotion, make it more accurate in meaning or emotionally.

VI. Conclusion

Through this survey and research, we understand the development status of machine translation and human translation both at home and abroad, investigate and analyze a variety of problems existing in the two and the gap between them, and find out the corresponding solutions. By selecting several chapters of literary works for manual translation and machine translation, we studies and compares the accuracy and fluency of the two translations in literary texts, and analyzes their limitations and future development trends. In the former, there are errors in word discrimination and the choice of articles, and the most serious errors are in the translation of proverbs. Chinese culture is so extensive and profound that machines alone cannot translate the deep meaning of sentences. The latter's problem of "low efficiency, high price" is obvious. Combining the form of the questionnaire and the options of the respondents to seek solutions. After sorting and in-depth discussion, we found reasonable solutions and relevant measures for the problems existing in machine translation and human translation, hoping to provide data and strategy help for related research.

References

- [1] Matheus Araújo, Adriano Pereira & Fabrício Benevenuto. A comparative study of machine translation for multilingual sentence-level sentiment analysis[J]. *Information Sciences*, 2020.
- [2] HUANG Jun-yan, DENG Mei-bao, HUANG Jia-min, LIANG Qi-lin, KONG Hai-qing, YANG Shu. A Comparative Study of Machine Translation and Human Translation—Take the evaluative meaning of words in "The Siege" as an example[J]. *English Abroad*, 2021(03).
- [3] Definition of Machine Translation: <https://baike.so.com/doc/6004715-6217698.html>
- [4] WU Jian-lan, ZHU Hang-hui, HUANG Yu-ting. Differences between machine translation and human translation from the perspective of literary texts[J]. *Taste Classics*, 2018(04).
- [5] WU Jian-lan, ZHANG Luo, ZHU Hang-hui. The Difference between Machine Translation and Human Translation - Taking Literary Texts as an Example[J]. *English Abroad*, 2018(06).
- [6] ZHAO Li-na. The Differences between machine Translation and human Translation and the future[J]. *School of Foreign Languages, Changchun Normal University*, 2019.
- [7] WEI Yue. Mistranslation caused by polysemy of English words in English-Chinese translation[J]. *School of Foreign Languages, Shenyang Normal University*, 2013(01).
- [8] WEI Hui-lin. On the problems of machine translation[N]. *Journal of Fuqing Branch of Fujian Normal University*, Issue 3, 2006 (1).

- [9] XU Jian-ping. On accuracy and readability of machine translation[J]. Chinese interpreter, 1998, 5: 47-49.
- [10] GAO Jie. The Role of Translator's initiative in poetry translation[J]. Journal of Kaifeng Education Institute, 2014(11).
- [11] YUE Chun-fang, WANG Li-jun, ZHANG Tian-wei. Problems and countermeasures in Machine translation[J]. Journal of Hebei Normal University, 2005(4).

Attachment: Questionnaire survey

1: Your status as a (single option) student

students

Others

2: Your age (single option) post-00s

after 00s

after 90s

after 80s

after 70s

3: Is the profession or occupation related to translation?

Yes

No

4: How often do you use translation software? (single choice)

Often

once in a while

very few

never

5: Do you think the relationship between machine translation and human translation will become? (single choice)

Competitive relationship

A symbiotic relationship

Helping each other

One of them will disappear

6: What translation do you think is the main trust in foreign exchange in daily life? (single option)

Human translation

Machine translation

7: What translation do you think should be relied upon in formal foreign exchanges? (single option)

Human translation

Machine translation

8: Which translation software are you currently using? (multiple choices)

Baidu

Youdao

Google

others

9: What problems do you think exist in machine translation?

The quality (accuracy) of translation needs to be improved. (multiple choices)

Software design is inconvenient to use.

Some software is overcharged.

10: What do you think are the advantages of machine translation? (Multiple choices)

Quick and convenient

High practicability

High accuracy

Others

11: What do you think are the advantages of human translation? (Multiple choices)

More flexible thinking

Syntactic analysis has fewer errors, more reasonable sentence structure and higher accuracy

More readable

Able to effectively deal with cultural differences and make them more authentic

Others

12: What problems do you think exist in human translation? (Multiple choice)

High charge

Slow and inefficient

Understanding deviation

The quality of translation varies widely

Others

13: What impact do you think translation software has on your English learning?

Too much dependence is not good for English learning

Saving a lot of time is worth learning

Provide ideas, but don't rely on them too much

There are misleading errors. Take everything with a grain of salt

14: Do you think the machine translation used is accurate?

Accurate

Basic accurate

Inaccurate

15: What do you think should be improved in cash machine translation?(multiple choices)

Increase accuracy

Word order grammar problems

16: How do you think the boom in the machine translation market will affect human translation?(fill in the blanks)